

Skills development and industrial transformation in Vietnam: The relationship between the TVET system and industry

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Vietnam #2 (2021)

At a glance:

This policy brief examines the relationship between industry and institutions of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Vietnam from the perspective of industry. It explores four main issues namely: (1) industrial transformation; (2) skills; (3) the role of skills on the transformational process and (4) the image of the TVET system. The findings indicate that:

- Over the last five years, there has been a manufacturing industrial transformation in Vietnam including three changes, namely (1) technology, (2) organization and (3) products. Technological change has triggered the change of organization and products.
- Four key factors have impacted on this transformation: (1) quality of human resources, (2) attitude of employees, (3) finance and (4) market forces.
- Greater transformations require greater skilled workers. TVET qualifications are a priority in the recruitment process and in promotion and supply has not kept pace.
- Training and up-skilling employees, through workplace training is the best solution to the immediate skills shortage.
- The quality of TVET graduates does not meet industry requirements due to the loose and informal relationship between the TVET system and industry, the quality of TVET staff and, their outdated machines and technologies.

Based on these findings, there are three important recommendations for TVET policymakers in Vietnam.

- As workplace training is the main method of training and upskilling for employees and the appearance of TVET providers is limited, quality assurance of workplace training programs should be considered seriously and included in the vocational education law. The role of in-company trainers should be taken into consideration.
- The loose and informal relationship between TVET providers and industry suggests that it may be necessary to change, update or add to the acts in the Vocational Education Law 2014. This could mean an industry driven model such as those in the UK or Australia. Alternatively, this relationship could be legally clarified, identifying the rights and responsibilities of each party, based on the German model.
- The “Teaching Factory” model as developed by Chryssolouris, Mavrikios and Mourtzis (2013) should be considered as a means to bring the real factory life into the classroom.

Introduction:

Vietnam has opened its door to the world and launched its first economic reforms since 1986. From that time to 2020, the GDP of Vietnam has grown approximately ten times, from 26.337 billion USD in 1986 to 261.921 billion USD in 2019 (World Bank, 2020). This achievement has lifted Vietnam

from the category of poor country to the category of lower developing country. There have been many investigations (Baum, 2020; Glewwe, Agrawal and Dollar, 2004; Van, 2018; Stefan, 2017) which seek to explain this great achievement.

This second policy brief from the Skills for Industry project examines one of the aspects that contribute to Vietnam's economic growth: the role of skills in the transformational process. Why is the aspect of skills selected on the issue of transformation? According to Chryssolouris et al. (2013), "society is always appreciative of skills. Several studies have revealed the relationship between educational quality and economic growth, highlighting the fact that human capital is a key to growth".

As the TVET system in Vietnam is mainly intended to produce the skilled workforce to serve the needs of industry, the relationship between industry and TVET providers is explored from the perspective of industry. To understand clearly the role of skills on transformation and the relationship between two sides, four research questions are raised:

1. What forces drive or hinder industrial transformation?
2. How do companies deal with the shortage of skilled workers?
3. How is the TVET system viewed by the manufacturing industries?
4. What is the importance of skills for industrial transformation?

To answer these questions, we utilized structured in-depth interview questions combined with quantitative questions to gather data from human resource managers and production managers at 18 manufacturing companies. This data was then transcribed into English and analyzed using Nvivo software, version 12. These case studies are part of the "Skills for Industry" project conducted to explore the contribution of TVET programmes to industrial growth and transformation of manufacturing companies. Prior to the case studies, a contextual analysis and survey of companies were conducted, based on which a first policy brief was published here: <https://phzh.ch/en/Research/skills->

for-industry/publications/.

Insights:

1. Transformation

In line with the previous policy brief, interview data indicates that the Garment, Electronics and Fish processing industries are undergoing transformation, including changes in technology, organization and products. 35 out of 36 interviewees stated that a change in technology had occurred in their company; 14 out of 36 reported a change in products; and 30 out of 36 respondents reported a change in organization. Technological change has been seen by industries as the trigger point to push changes in products and organization. Four factors have influenced this transformation.

The first factor is the quality of human resources. According to the human resource manager of a garment company (VG7 HR) technological change has driven changes in organization and products which require a more highly-skilled workforce:

"When technology is changing, the organizational structure and products also are. There is a cause and effect relationship among the technology, organization and product changes. When applying new technology in the production process, **the quality of the human resource is the vital factor to promote these changes.**"
(VG 7 HR)

The second factor, attitude of employees, is closely related to the previous issue and captures the extent to which employees allow companies to introduce new technology. This especially relates to those holding high positions, and it is impacted by age: "old people don't like but young people like to change".

"It means that one of the most important factors in the change is the attitude of the leaders, the team leaders and the technicians." (VE 8 HR)

“The company respects and thinks of them firstly when we are going to change the technology and making a new product. The big challenge is that, they often hold an important position in the production department. If they want to change then that’s great. However, if they are afraid of changing, it is also difficult.” (VG 1 HR)

The third factor is finance. Companies acknowledged costs related to changing technology, suggesting that this made change hard. However, companies also mentioned that increasing labor costs will lead to technological and other changes. They want increased productivity so must invest to buy or upgrade technology.

“It is about finance. We give 5 to 10% of revenue to develop and transfer technology. However, this fund is still not enough.” (VE 173 HR)

“...sustainable development and transformation are impacted by many factors such as financial issues, the quality of human resource, the strategy of a company, the support from Government. The skills of employees are just one of the factors that help a company to develop sustainably and be ready for transformation.” (VF 178 HR)

The final factor is market demand. This is linked to the need to change products. Respondents indicated that they adopted new forms of technology to address the needs of customers, and the competitiveness of the market.

“In recent years, the scale of company development has increased a bit. We are equipped with a number of modern technology machines due to the requirements of customers and market. We can shorten the production time.” (VF 211 HR)

“Increasing productivity is very important. Because, it meets the requirements of markets and partners. If we cannot meet the requirements, the customers will leave us. That time, it is hard to say the company will develop.” (VE 86 HR)

2. Skills

Transformation “is related to skills” and “the core of the matter is to change the skills of staff”.

“Any changes always require the skills of employees. It is not only requirement from the managerial level but also to all other levels. For example, if someone is moved to a new position, they at least have to learn the skill of team work. If they are moved to a higher position such as team leader, they need to know how the management and leadership skills are.”

We also found that workplace training is considered “the most valuable” for training newcomers and up-skilling employees (VE 157 HR). The same representative explains that,

“All modules or subjects are designed for forming the skills that meet the company’s requirements instantly. In addition, the experienced and skilled employees in the company transfer skills to new comers are the best way. The first reason is that these people have known each other and working together, so they more easily share information. The second one, the company will save money, time and human resource in the production process.”

The appearance of TVET providers in this process is further limited as, when transferring new technology and new machines, experts from the machine providers have been seen as the trainers to deliver new knowledge and skills to the experienced,

skilled employees and company leaders. Then, these persons will train the lower levels or newcomers. This leads companies to depend fully on machine providers in the process of technological change.

3. The role of skills on transformation

The findings show that when companies have a plan for transformation, new skills and upskilling for all levels of employees are the big issue for companies to consider. Two central themes have appeared.

First, greater transformations require a greater skilled workforce.

“We want our workers to have more skills. When they have more skills, they will do a better job and meet the requirements of the company. Also, whenever we upgrade technology or change products, people who had more skills will adapt more quickly than those without skills or with lower skills.” (VE 43 Pro)

Second, employees holding TVET qualifications are a priority, for recruitment, industrial transformation and promotion.

“They already have got the knowledge and skills when they’re taking the courses at the TVET providers. The company does not need to train them more. They also understand the basics of the real working life due to their internship time at industry. When changing technology, we look to them firstly.” (VF 4 Pro)

4. The image of the TVET system

In Vietnam, the TVET system has the responsibility to provide the skilled human resources to meet the requirements of industry and society. The findings indicate that the TVET system is perceived both positively and negatively for different aspects.

For the positive side, three main themes emerged.

The first one, the manufacturing industries have trusted the TVET system as the place to produce the high-skilled labor workforce for them. Secondly, industries prefer educated people from the TVET providers to unskilled people. Finally, they have some useful specific programs to help the development of companies.

“Employees with TVET qualifications have helped the company to improve the quality of the human resource, especially when the company wants to apply the new technologies and operate the new machines.” (VF 211 HR)

“All qualifications from diploma to the bachelor degree in Information technology, telecommunication, electronics and computer science are useful.” (VE 43 Pro)

On the negative side, firstly, industries pointed out that quality of graduates (quality includes the technical and social behavioral skills) does not meet the requirements of industries.

“All candidates with the TVET qualifications need more practical and soft skills as at the TVET providers they don’t provide enough skills and updated equipment for students to practice.” (VE 15 HR)

“In general, the vocational training system in Vietnam, from certificate levels to the university degree, the graduates only meet 20% to 30% of the requirements of the companies. So, our recruitment process is extremely difficult.” (VE 42 HR)

Secondly, industries indicated that poor facilities (including outdated machines and technology), the limited, informal and one way relationship between

the TVET providers and industries, and the quality of the lecturers, have all impacted the skills of students from TVET providers:

“The technology and machines at the school are behind us about 20 to 30 years.” (VE 42HR)

“We have not related with the TVET providers in any ways such as selection, design and assessment the training programs. We only receive some requests from the TVET providers. They see the company as the place for the students to come here to practice.” (VE 43 Pro)

“We do not want to comment about the quality of the staff at the TVET providers. It is a sensitive issue. They have theory but the lecturers do not have enough practical experiences. They do not have much time to work as the real workers, so they do not clearly understand the manufacturing process at the company. One more important point is that most of them have never made products that meet the requirements of customers. So, this raises the question of how confident are they to teach the students about these products?” (VG 81 Pro)

This raises the question of why the involvement of TVET providers in industrial transformation is limited. It could be the TVET system is not highly valued by manufacturing industries. This suggests policymakers considering reforming the TVET system could draw, for improving skills of students, on the final assessments of an independent third party.

4. Conclusions and recommendations to the TVET policy makers:

From the perspective of manufacturing industries, skills including socio-emotional and technical skills of employees have been seen as the key factor to

make industrial transformation (World Bank, 2021). To quickly solve the shortage of skilled workers, industries have seen workplace training as the best way to train their newcomers and up-skill employees. This suggests that quality assurance of workplace training should be taken into consideration.

Presently in Vietnam, the TVET system is the main producer of skilled workers to serve the needs of society and industry. However, the TVET system is not highly valued by manufacturing industries due to the loose and informal relationship between the TVET providers and industries, the quality of staff in the TVET system and the outdated machines and technology at TVET providers.

Perhaps policy makers need to consider a different approach to training the skilled labor workforce to rapidly meet the needs of industry and society. This policy brief recommends a closer relationship between TVET providers and industry, harnessing existing workplace training skills by drawing on the model of the “Teaching factory”. In the future, training and up-skilling of the workforce could be driven by industries and assessment of skills training could be conducted by an independent third party such as the occupational associations instead of the TVET system.

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